

28 **1. Introduction**

29 The study of long-term sea level variability is usually undertaken either from tide gauge
30 and satellite altimetry observations or from model hindcasts of the last decades.
31 Observations provide very valuable information on sea level. However, their limited
32 coverage in space (e.g. tide gauges) or in time (e.g. altimetry) makes difficult to
33 understand the physical processes driving long-term sea level variability. A better
34 understanding of such processes can be achieved by combining the more accurate
35 information on sea level provided by observations with the more complete process
36 information given by baroclinic models.

37 Indeed an advantage of the models is that they provide information on different
38 oceanographic variables, which can be used to study not only sea level variability but
39 also the mechanisms driving such variability. However, models also suffer from some
40 deficiencies. One of these deficiencies is that they can lead to a poor representation of
41 the mean circulation and variability. For instance, comparisons with altimetry data
42 [McClean *et al.*, 1997] have shown that the POP model, with a resolution of $1/6^\circ$,
43 captures about 60% of the altimetric sea surface height variability at global scale. Also
44 in the Mediterranean Sea several authors [Calafat *et al.*, 2009; Tsimplis *et al.*, 2009]
45 have studied sea level variability as given by regional models, finding that they perform
46 rather poorly in reproducing sea level trends and variability, especially at mesoscale.
47 The poor performance of the regional models found by the aforementioned authors is in
48 part due to the fact that the analyzed models are eddy-permitting rather than eddy-
49 resolving and, thus, they are not capable of reproducing the mesoscale.

50 The spatial resolution is precisely a major handicap when dealing with the
51 Mediterranean Sea, as it has a strong impact on the accuracy of convection and
52 thermohaline circulation representation [Herrmann *et al.*, 2008]. Also, the exchanges

53 through the Gibraltar Strait, which are a key element of the Mediterranean system,
54 require a high spatial resolution for an accurate description [*Sannino et al.*, 2009]. This
55 is why global models with coarse resolution could lead to a poor representation of the
56 main physical processes occurring in the Mediterranean Sea. On the other hand,
57 regional models can be implemented with higher resolution, though open boundaries at
58 which flow conditions are not known can constitute a problem to reproduce the long
59 term variability.

60 A lot of efforts have been devoted during the last decade to the development of regional
61 models aimed at reproducing the main physical processes occurring in the
62 Mediterranean Sea with enough accuracy [*Somot et al.*, 2006; *Somot and Colin*, 2008;
63 *Sannino et al.*, 2009; *Artale et al.*, 2009]. Most of these works have focused on the study
64 of water mass properties, processes of dense water formation and circulation, paying
65 much less attention to the sea level variability inferred from the models.

66 Mediterranean sea level variability is driven by atmospheric mechanical forcing [*Gomis*
67 *et al.*, 2008] and changes in the thermohaline properties (steric component), as well as
68 mass variations in the long term [*Calafat et al.*, 2010]. The atmospheric mechanical
69 forcing of Mediterranean sea level is reasonably well understood and characterized (see
70 for instance *Gomis et al.*, 2008). The mass component is the most difficult one to
71 quantify, since direct (gravimetry) observations (GRACE mission) are only available
72 since 2002 and with a low spatial resolution (about 1000 km) (for past decades it has
73 been indirectly inferred as non-steric sea level; see for instance *Calafat et al.*, 2010) and
74 there is no model able to completely account for it. The mass component in the
75 Mediterranean is mainly affected by mass redistribution in the Atlantic (e.g. due to
76 winds) and, eventually, by the contribution of the continental ice melting. Global
77 models are, in principle, capable of reproducing the mass redistribution but they do not

78 account for the contribution of the ice melting. Conversely, the steric component of sea
79 level, which induces a significant part of sea level variance (about 30% at inter-annual
80 scales; *Calafat et al.*, 2010), can be estimated from in situ observations or 3D baroclinic
81 models.

82 The steric component depends on the evolution of the water masses properties inside the
83 basin, which in turn depends on the surface heat and freshwater fluxes, the river run-off
84 and the exchanges through the Gibraltar and the Dardanelles straits. A key process for
85 the steric component is the heat and salt transfer from surface to the deepest layers,
86 which is partly controlled by convection linked to deep and intermediate water
87 formation [*Leaman and Schott*, 1991; *Mertens and Schott*, 1998; *Grignon et al.*, 2010]
88 and partly by diffusion. Several authors (e.g., *Vigo et al.*, 2005; *Calafat and Gomis*,
89 2009) have shown that the decadal variability of the Mediterranean sea level is related
90 to processes such as the Eastern Mediterranean Transient (EMT, *Roether et al.*, 1996,
91 2007). The EMT started during the eighties, when the deepest parts of the Eastern basin
92 were filled with very dense water of Aegean origin that lifted up the older bottom
93 waters of Adriatic origin and changed in a few years the water mass structure of the
94 region. Hydrological observations showed that the increased dense water formation in
95 the Aegean Sea started in 1987 and reached maximum values in 1993 [*Theocharis et*
96 *al.*, 1999]. After 1995 the situation returned back to normal: the Aegean Sea returned to
97 pre-EMT conditions, exporting small amounts of dense water that do not reach the
98 bottom of the Ionian and the Levantine basins [*Theocharis et al.*, 2002] while the
99 Adriatic Sea became again the main contributor to the dense waters of the Eastern
100 Mediterranean [*Klein et al.*, 2000; *Manca et al.*, 2006]. These changes in the
101 thermohaline circulation of the basin clearly reflected on regional sea level changes
102 such as the marked negative trends observed in the Ionian Sea and the strong positive

103 trends observed in the Aegean Sea during the altimetric period 1993-2000 [*Cazenave et*
104 *al.*, 2001; *Fenoglio-Marc*, 2002; *Vigo et al.*, 2005; *Criado-Aldeanueva et al.*, 2008;
105 *Calafat and Gomis*, 2009].

106 As commented above, long term estimates of total and steric sea level from
107 observations are limited by the poor sampling. Models could help to fill that gap, but
108 their ability to reproduce the key processes must be demonstrated. Moreover, estimates
109 of sea level evolution under future climate change scenarios also rely on numerical
110 models, which strengthens the importance of a proper evaluation of their skills. Thus,
111 the purpose of this paper is twofold: 1) to validate hindcasts of the Mediterranean Sea
112 and determine the weakest and the strongest points of the simulations in reproducing sea
113 level variability, and 2) to identify which factors have a stronger impact on the
114 modelling of Mediterranean sea level variability and check whether their simulation can
115 be improved to obtain more accurate sea level results. To accomplish it, we compare the
116 outputs of three baroclinic models of the Mediterranean Sea: an ocean-ice coupled
117 forced global model that includes the Mediterranean Sea, a regional model forced by
118 high resolution atmospheric data and a regional atmosphere-ocean coupled model. The
119 comparison focuses on water mass properties (temperature and salinity), water mass
120 formation and on the derived steric and total sea level. In Section 2, we describe the
121 datasets and the preliminary processing. The outputs of the models are validated against
122 temperature, salinity and sea level observations in Section 3. In Section 4 we summarize
123 the main results and discuss the implications of these results, identifying the factors that
124 have a stronger impact on the modelling of the Mediterranean sea level variability.
125 Finally, in Section 5 we present the main conclusions.

126

127 **2. Data sets**

128 **2.1 Altimetry data set**

129 Gridded Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) fields were collected from the merged AVISO
130 products that are available at <http://www.aviso.oceanobs.com>. The AVISO regional
131 product for the Mediterranean Sea consists of multimission (up to four satellites at a
132 given time) gridded sea surface heights. The data span the period between November
133 1992 and December 2008, with a spatial resolution of $1/8^\circ \times 1/8^\circ$ and weekly time
134 resolution. All the standard corrections (tides, wet/dry troposphere, ionosphere) were
135 applied to altimetry data [Benada, 1997]. The atmospheric correction was also applied
136 in order to minimize aliasing effects [Volkov *et al.*, 2007]. Therefore, SLA as provided
137 by altimetry corresponds to total sea level minus the atmospheric contribution (i.e, steric
138 and mass components). Satellite altimetry data also require a specific correction to
139 compensate for the Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA). For the GIA satellite correction
140 we used the ICE-5G VM2 model described in the work by *Peltier* [2004].

141 **2.2 The reconstruction data set**

142 The total sea level fields used for the period 1961-2000 have been obtained from the
143 reconstruction carried out by *Calafat and Gomis* [2009]. That reconstruction consists of
144 monthly $1/4^\circ \times 1/4^\circ$ gridded fields covering the Mediterranean Sea. Sea level fields are
145 reconstructed combining spatial Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) computed
146 from altimetry data and long tide gauge records in a reduced-space optimal interpolation
147 scheme [Church *et al.*, 2004]. Because model data do not include sea level variations
148 due to the mechanical forcing of the atmospheric pressure, this has also been removed
149 from the reconstructed fields using sea level pressure fields from the National Centers
150 for Environmental Prediction [NCEP; Kalnay *et al.*, 1996]. Therefore, it is important to
151 note that the sea level from the reconstruction accounts for both the steric and the mass
152 components of sea level but not for the effect of the atmospheric pressure. Concerning

153 the accuracy of the reconstruction, *Calafat and Jordà* [2011] have estimated a RMS
154 error of 1.4 cm for the mean sea level.

155 **2.3 The Hydrographic data base**

156 The hydrographic data set used in this work was obtained by combining two
157 hydrographic data bases: the Mediterranean data base MEDAR and the global Ishii data
158 base. MEDAR consists of yearly temperature and salinity fields on a $1/5^\circ \times 1/5^\circ$ grid
159 covering the Mediterranean basin and spanning the period 1945-2002 [*Rixen et al.*,
160 2005]. The vertical domain extends down to over 4000 m, with data on 25 standard
161 levels. The gridded fields were obtained applying a variational inverse method to
162 interpolate in situ temperature and salinity observations [*Rixen et al.*, 2001]. It is worth
163 noting here that, because in the MEDAR data set the annual means were computed
164 without having removed previously the seasonal cycle, part of the intra-seasonal
165 variability can be poured into inter-annual scales, especially when the spatial and
166 temporal distribution of the data is particularly sparse. As a consequence of this, the
167 MEDAR data show unrealistic large variability in the upper layers,

168 The Ishii data set is more recent and consists of monthly $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ gridded global
169 temperature and salinity fields [*Ishii et al.*, 2009]; hence, a monthly seasonal cycle can
170 be subtracted to the data prior to the computation of annual means. The gridded fields
171 span the period 1945-2006 and cover from surface to 700 m. They result from applying
172 an objective analysis to different kinds of in situ ocean temperature and salinity data
173 (e.g., bottle, CTD and ARGO float data); XBT and MBT data are previously submitted
174 to the corresponding time-varying depth bias correction. The Ishii data set also includes
175 an estimation of the errors associated with the interpolation of the temperature and
176 salinity gridded fields. Due to the unrealistic large variability exhibited by the MEDAR
177 data in the upper layers, we decided to use Ishii data for the upper 700 m and MEDAR

178 data for lower levels (where the impact of the seasonal cycle is negligible). The merged
179 data base will be hereinafter referred to as the MEDISH database.

180 In order to compute the steric sea level, the specific volume anomaly ($\Delta\alpha$) must be first
181 estimated as:

$$182 \quad \Delta\alpha = \frac{1}{\rho(S,T,P)} - \frac{1}{\rho(35,0,P)} \quad (1)$$

183 where T is the temperature, S is the Salinity, P the pressure, and $\rho(35,0,P)$ is the
184 density of a water mass at pressure P , a temperature of 0°C and a salinity of 35 psu. The
185 steric component of sea level (Z_s) can then be computed as the vertical integration of
186 the specific volume anomaly ($\Delta\alpha$):

$$187 \quad Z_s = -\frac{1}{g} \int_{P_f}^{P_o} \Delta\alpha \cdot dp \quad (2)$$

188 where g is the gravitational acceleration, and P_o and P_f are the pressure values at surface
189 and at a reference level, respectively. The steric sea level has been computed only for
190 the upper 700 m covered by the Ishii database. There are several reasons for that: first,
191 monthly data are only available for the upper 700 m; second, the Ishii data set provides
192 error estimates for the temperature and salinity gridded products, which can be used to
193 compute the uncertainty associated with the computation of the steric component by
194 following the methodology used by *Calafat et al.* [2010]. Finally, *Tsimplis and Rixen*
195 [2002] suggested that salinity measurements at deep layers may not be very reliable and
196 that steric sea level variability in the Mediterranean Sea is driven by changes in the top
197 400 m.

198 **2.4 Model data**

199 In this paper we compare the long-term sea level variability given by three baroclinic
200 numerical models: an ocean-ice coupled free-surface global model [*Barnier et al.*,
201 2006], a regional rigid-lid ocean model [*Somot et al.*, 2006] and a regional atmosphere-
202 ocean coupled free-surface model [*Artale et al.*, 2009]. Those models have been
203 selected because they offer a wide variety of choices in the treatment of open boundary
204 conditions, model spatial resolution and forcings. It is important to highlight that our
205 aim is not to describe processes, but to understand why different simulations perform
206 differently. Therefore, even if the chosen simulations are not the most update products,
207 they are well suited to fulfill our goals. It is worth mentioning that none of the models is
208 eddy-resolving, but eddy-permitting and, thus, they can not properly resolve the
209 mesoscale. The computation of the sea level is different depending on whether the
210 model uses a free-surface or a rigid-lid formulation. In the free-surface formulation, the
211 sea surface height (η) is obtained as the solution of the prognostic equation:

$$212 \quad \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} = -D + P - E \quad (3)$$

213 where $P - E$ is the precipitation minus evaporation budget, and D is defined as:

$$214 \quad D = \vec{\nabla} \cdot [(H + \eta)\vec{U}] \quad (4)$$

215 where H is the depth of the ocean bottom and \vec{U} is the depth-average velocity.

216 In the rigid-lid formulation, the free surface height is replaced by the pressure against
217 the rigid-lid p_s , which is related to the pressure p by

$$218 \quad p(z) = p_s + \int_z^0 \rho g dz' \quad (5)$$

219 The sea surface height, η , is related to p_s by the equality $\eta = p_s / \rho_s g$, where ρ_s is the
220 sea surface density.

221 All three models used in this study use the Boussinesq approximation and, thus, they
222 conserve volume rather than mass. As a consequence of this, they yield correct relative
223 horizontal sea surface height gradients, but a spatially uniform time-varying factor must
224 be applied in order to adjust the sea level provided by the models for any net expansion
225 or contraction due to heating or cooling [Greatbatch, 1994]. This factor is simply the
226 steric effect computed from top to bottom and averaged over the whole domain of the
227 model. Also steric sea level has been computed from the temperature and salinity fields
228 provided by the models, following the same methodology than for the hydrographic
229 data bases. In order to make the comparisons between the steric from the models and
230 that from the hydrographic observations (see Section 2.3) consistent the reference depth
231 was chosen at 700 m.

232 The characteristics of the three models are presented in the following; for an easier
233 comparison, they have been summarized in Table 1.

234 *a) ORCA simulation*

235 This global hind-cast simulation is based on the eddy-permitting ORCA025
236 configuration [Barnier *et al.*, 2006], described in detail in *DRAKKAR group* [2007].
237 ORCA025 model is based on a global configuration of the NEMO modelling system in
238 its free surface version [Roullet and Madec, 2000]. The model is implemented on a grid
239 with a spatial resolution of $1/4^\circ \times 1/4^\circ$. It uses 46 vertical levels unevenly distributed
240 with a resolution varying from 6 m near the surface to 250 m at the bottom, with partial
241 steps in the lowest level. The specific hindcast experiment used here is the ORCA025-
242 G70 and the period spanned by this simulation is 1958-2004. Hereinafter we will refer
243 to this simulation as the ORCA simulation.

244 A Laplacian lateral isopycnal diffusion and a biharmonic viscosity are used for tracers
245 ($300 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ at the equator and decreasing poleward, proportionally to the grid size) and
246 momentum ($-1.5 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$), respectively. For the vertical mixing a modified version
247 of the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) parameterisation for the vertical mixing
248 coefficient that includes the effects of long waves, Langmuir cells and the penetration of
249 TKE in depth are used [Molines *et al.*, 2006]. In case of static instability, vertical
250 diffusion is enhanced up to $10 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

251 ORCA025-G70 was forced by the DRAKKAR Forcing Set No. 3 [DFS3, Molines *et al.*,
252 2006; Brodeau *et al.*, 2010]. DFS3 radiation fluxes are based on the Coordinated
253 Ocean-Ice Reference Experiments (CORE) forcing [Large and Yeager, 2004]. Monthly
254 precipitation fields are based on a blend between the uncorrected and standard CORE
255 products, with the blend occurring between 20 and 30° N . Air temperature, wind and air
256 humidity are 6-hourly ERA40-reanalysis fields (1958-2001) and ECMWF (2002-2004).
257 The spatial resolution of the atmospheric forcing is $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$. The model bathymetry is
258 derived from the 2-minute resolution Etopo2 bathymetry file of NGDC (National
259 Geophysical Data Center).

260 Initial conditions for temperature and salinity are derived from the NODC World Ocean
261 Atlas (1998, [http:// www.cdc.noaa.gov/](http://www.cdc.noaa.gov/)) for the middle and low latitudes and from the
262 Medatlas climatology [Jourdan *et al.*, 1998] for the Mediterranean Sea. Initial
263 conditions for sea ice are based off a previous ORCA025 experiment using
264 climatological CORE forcing [Molines *et al.*, 2006]. A climatological seasonal runoff is
265 provided for the most important rivers and ice-covered regions. A restoring to
266 climatological sea surface salinity (SSS) is used in the ORCA025-G70 run with a
267 timescale of 60 days for the upper two vertical levels. No spin-up is performed in this
268 simulation.

269 ***b) OM8 simulation***

270 The OPAMED8 baroclinic model used by *Somot et al.* [2006] is a rigid-lid model that
271 covers the Mediterranean Sea with a spatial resolution of $1/8^\circ \times 1/8^\circ \cos(\textit{latitude})$ in the
272 horizontal and 43 non-uniform Z-levels in the vertical. It is based on a limited-area
273 version of the OPA model [*Madec et al.*, 1998]. The 40-year simulation (1961-2001)
274 will be hereinafter referred to as the OM8 simulation.

275 The horizontal eddy diffusivity and viscosity coefficients are fixed to $-1.2 \times 10^{10} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$
276 for tracers and dynamics by means of a biharmonic operator. A 1.5 turbulent closure
277 scheme is used for the vertical eddy diffusivity and the vertical diffusion is enhanced to
278 $1 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ in case of unstable stratification [*Somot et al.*, 2006]. The bathymetry is based on
279 the ETOPO5'x5' data base [*Smith and Sandwell*, 1997].

280 The initial conditions are provided by the MEDATLAS-II monthly climatology for the
281 Mediterranean Sea [*MEDAR Group*, 2002] and by a seasonal climatology [*Reynaud et*
282 *al.*, 1998] for the Atlantic part of the model. The simulation starts in August and then a
283 20 years spin-up is performed by forcing the model two times successively by the inter-
284 annual fluxes of the 1960-1970 period. The atmospheric forcing is a high resolution
285 dynamical downscaling of the ERA-40 reanalysis. The downscaling (described by
286 *Herrmann and Somot*, 2008) was carried out with a regional version of the ARPEGE-
287 Climate model [*Déqué and Piedelievre*, 1995] that uses a stretched and tilted grid
288 resulting in a horizontal resolution of about 50 km over the Mediterranean Sea. Air-sea
289 fluxes (heat, water and momentum) were extracted from the atmospheric simulation at a
290 daily time scale. A first validation of the air-sea flux dataset has been done in *Herrmann*
291 *and Somot* [2008] for the case study of the 1986-87 winter.

292 Additional forcings of the OM8 simulation are climatological values (with an annual
293 cycle) for the river runoff, the Black Sea inflow and the Atlantic Ocean characteristics.
294 The latter consist of a 3D relaxation for temperature and salinity applied in a buffer
295 zone extending beyond the western limits of the Iberian Peninsula (11°W). Hence,
296 eventual sea level trends occurring beyond the Atlantic boundary of the domain are not
297 taken into account. The surface heat flux is adjusted to the model sea surface
298 temperature (SST) by a relaxation towards the daily SST used by the regional version of
299 the ARPEGE atmosphere model. The relaxation coefficient is $-40 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{K})$, which is
300 equivalent to an 8-day restoring time. The fact that no SSS relaxation is applied in OM8
301 means that the inter-annual variability of the SSS is free, which represents a significant
302 improvement compared to state-of-the-art Mediterranean Sea models.

303 *c) MITgcm simulation*

304 This simulation has been performed using the regional coupled system PROTHEUS
305 [Artale *et al.*, 2009] for the Mediterranean basin. The PROTHEUS system is composed
306 of the RegCM3 atmospheric regional model and the MITgcm ocean model, coupled
307 through the OASIS3 coupler. Hereinafter, we will refer to this simulation as the
308 MITgcm simulation.

309 The stand-alone oceanic component has been recently implemented and validated by
310 Sannino *et al.* [2009]. It is based on the MITgcm developed by Marshall *et al.*
311 [1997a,b], which is used in its hydrostatic, implicit free-surface, partial step topography
312 formulation. The ocean model has a spatial resolution of $1/8^\circ \times 1/8^\circ$ and 42 vertical
313 levels with a resolution varying from 10 m at the surface to 300 m in the deeper part of
314 the basin. Horizontal viscous and diffusive terms are modelled with a bi-harmonic
315 formulation with diffusivity and viscosity coefficients equal to $1.5 \times 10^{10} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$. Vertical
316 eddy-diffusivity is modelled via a Laplacian formulation with a diffusivity coefficient

317 ranging from 3.0×10^{-5} m s at the surface to 1.0×10^{-7} m s at the ocean bottom. The
318 viscous coefficient is kept constant at 1.5×10^{-4} m²/s over the whole water column. The
319 vertical diffusion is locally enhanced to 1 m²/s in regions where the stratification
320 becomes unstable. The bottom topography is interpolated from the 1/12° ETOPO5
321 database (US National Geophysical Data Centre) with some corrections made for
322 isolated grid points located in correspondence of islands and straits; in particular the
323 Strait of Gibraltar was modified to be represented by two grid points in latitude. The
324 period spanned by the simulation is 1958-2001.

325 The simulation is initialized with MEDATLAS II [*MEDAR Group, 2002*] climatology
326 data for January, and then a 40-year spin-up is performed using a 3D relaxation of the
327 temperature and salinity to the climatological values. The two-way exchange through
328 Gibraltar is achieved by means of a box located west of Gibraltar, where a 3D relaxation
329 of the water mass characteristics to a monthly climatology [*Levitus, 1982*] is applied for
330 the Gulf of Cadiz in the first 30 grid points.

331 The atmospheric forcing is provided each 6 hours by the outputs of the RegCM3
332 atmospheric model with a spatial resolution of 30 km. The RegCM3 model is initialised
333 and forced in the open boundaries by ERA-40 reanalysis over the whole period. Except
334 for the Atlantic, where no surface forcing is applied, the MITgcm ocean model is forced
335 through the specification of wind stress and heat fluxes computed by RegCM3. In turn,
336 the SST used by the atmospheric model is taken from the ocean part. That is, no
337 relaxation in SST is needed, as far as atmospheric heat fluxes are in balance with the
338 oceanic evolution. Also, no relaxation in SSS is used in this simulation. An interactive
339 river scheme is used to provide the oceanic module with fresh water sources consistent
340 with the atmospheric branch of the simulated hydrological cycle. Natural boundary

341 conditions for salinity have been applied to the ocean module, which means that the net
342 freshwater is treated as a real fresh water flux.

343 **3. Results**

344 Results are presented in two parts: the first one is devoted to the study of water mass
345 properties. We first look at averaged values of temperature and salinity and their
346 temporal evolution. Then, we focus on dense water formation processes in the regions
347 of the Mediterranean Sea where it is most important, namely: the Gulf of Lions, and the
348 Aegean and Adriatic seas.

349 The second part focuses on total and steric sea level variability. Total sea level results
350 are presented for two different periods: 1993-2000 and 1961-2000; for the first period
351 (1993-2000) results are compared against altimetry observations, while for the long
352 period (1961-2000) we use the sea level reconstruction of *Calafat and Gomis* [2009].
353 Steric sea level obtained from models is validated against the steric sea level computed
354 from hydrographic observations. As a particularly relevant case, we have also analyzed
355 the performance of the models in reproducing the sea level changes observed during the
356 EMT period in the Aegean and Ionian Seas.

357

358 **3.1 Water mass properties**

359 *a) Averaged temperature and salinity*

360 Temperature and salinity have been averaged for the Western and Eastern basins. The
361 comparison is shown in four layers: 0-100 m, 100-500 m, 500-1000 m and 1000-2000
362 m and for detrended time series for the sake of comparison (Fig. 1). The biases between
363 the three models and the MEDISH climatology are given in Table 2, while the
364 temperature and salinity trends obtained from the models and MEDISH are given in

365 Table 3. Linear trends are computed using an MM-regression estimator [Yohai, 1987],
366 while standard errors associated to the regression coefficients are computed by means of
367 a robust bootstrap [Salibian-Barrera, 2006].

368 For the top 100 m and for both the Eastern and Western basins (Figs. 1a,b) the observed
369 temperature variability is in good agreement with that from all models. Observations-
370 model correlations are over 0.85 in both subbasins (quoted correlations are always
371 significant at the 95% confidence level, unless otherwise stated). The fact that the
372 averaged temperature from all models shows a very similar inter-annual variability in
373 the upper 100 m is not surprising as all models are run using an atmospheric forcing that
374 is derived from the ERA-40 reanalysis (the atmospheric forcing used to run the
375 MITgcm is provided by the outputs of the RegCM3 atmospheric model, which is
376 initialised and forced in the open boundaries by ERA-40 reanalysis over the whole
377 period). In the case of the OM8 model the atmospheric forcing is a high resolution
378 dynamical downscaling of the ERA-40 reanalysis while in the MITgcm it is provided by
379 the outputs of the RegCM3 atmospheric model, which is initialised and forced in the
380 open boundaries by the ERA-40 reanalysis. The ORCA model is directly forced by the
381 ERA-40 reanalysis. Regarding biases, the MITgcm model shows the largest temperature
382 bias in both the Eastern and the Western subbasins (-0.83 °C and -0.50 °C, respectively,
383 see Table 2). The OM8 is the model that shows the smallest bias in both subbasins (0.12
384 °C and 0.37 °C), probably because it is the only model that applies a SST relaxation.

385 For the layer 100-500 m, the models and the MEDISH averaged temperature variability
386 are overall in good agreement in both subbasins (Figs. 1a,b). The OM8 is the model
387 showing the highest correlations in the Western subbasin (0.91) while the ORCA model
388 is the one showing the highest correlation in the Eastern subbasin (0.84). In terms of
389 bias, the MITgcm is the model that better represents the time-mean temperature, with

390 deviations of only -0.07°C and -0.01°C in the Eastern and Western Mediterranean,
391 respectively (Table 2). A major feature observed in this layer is the cold period of the
392 Western Mediterranean between 1980 and 1990, which is clearly shown by MEDISH
393 and by the models.

394 For the layer 500-1000 m the model that better reproduces the major features of the
395 averaged temperature variability in the Eastern Mediterranean (Fig. 1a) is the MITgcm,
396 which has a correlation of 0.5 with observations and a bias of 0.18°C (Table 2). The
397 other two models do not describe this layer successfully in the Eastern Mediterranean.
398 In particular, although the time-mean temperature simulated by ORCA is in very good
399 agreement with MEDISH (the bias is only of 0.04°C), its variability is by far too
400 smoothed. In the Western Mediterranean both the MITgcm and the OM8 show a very
401 good agreement when compared with MEDISH (Fig. 1b), with correlations of 0.82 and
402 0.86, respectively. The ORCA model does not show a significant correlation with the
403 MEDISH temperature, again because of the smooth variability. The MITgcm shows the
404 smallest temperature bias (0.23°C), while the OM8 shows the largest one (0.63°C).

405 For the layer below 1000 m none of the models reproduce the MEDISH temperature
406 variability; the three of them and particularly ORCA show a very smooth behaviour
407 (Figs. 1a,b). The biases with respect to MEDISH are all smaller than in the upper layers,
408 the smallest one being that of the MITgcm model in both the Eastern and Western
409 basins (-0.02°C and 0.01°C respectively, see Table 2). It is interesting to notice that
410 according to observations, the cold period of the Western Mediterranean observed
411 during the 80's in the layers 100-500 m and 500-1000 m is also apparent below 1000 m,
412 though less marked. However, although MITgcm and OM8 succeed to capture the cold
413 period above 1000 m, none of them have a cold signal below that level. The fact that the
414 averaged temperature from the ORCA model shows no inter-annual variability below

415 500 m is probably related to the low resolution of both the model and the atmospheric
416 forcing. In the Mediterranean, the vertical heat redistribution is modulated by
417 mesoscale processes (e.g. eddies or slope currents meanderings). Moreover, the spatial
418 and temporal resolution of atmospheric fluxes also plays a crucial role in the
419 modellization of dense water formation [*Herrmann and Somot, 2008*]. Therefore, it is
420 expected that ORCA shows less variability in the vertical heat transfer and thus in the
421 temperature variability in the intermediate and deeper layers. This is further exemplified
422 by the fact that the MITgcm (with same spatial resolution than OM8 but higher
423 resolution of the atmospheric forcing) is the model showing both the largest temperature
424 variability below 1000 m and the highest rates of dense water formation (see Section
425 3.1d).

426 With regard to temperature trends, the most remarkable feature is the warming drift
427 shown by all models in the intermediate and deep layers, especially in the Western
428 Mediterranean (Table 3). In the layer 500-1000 m all models show large trends of up to
429 0.0130 °C/year in the Western subbasin, while the MEDISH trend is of only 0.0022
430 °C/year. Below 1000 m only the MITgcm and OM8 models show such a drift (0.0097
431 °C/year and 0.0062 °C/year, respectively). This warming trend will be responsible for
432 the unrealistic large sea level trends shown later in this paper.

433 The agreement between the salinity variability given by the models and by MEDISH is
434 not as good as for the temperature (Figs. 1c,d). In the Eastern Mediterranean none of the
435 models show significant correlations with MEDISH at any layer. In the Western
436 Mediterranean, the OM8 model shows a significant correlation of 0.4 in the upper layer,
437 and in the layer 500-1000 the MITgcm and OM8 models show correlations of 0.4 and
438 0.5, respectively. No significant correlation is found in the other layers. Regarding
439 biases, in the top 100 m, the ORCA model shows much fresher waters than MEDISH

440 and the other two models in both subbasins, with a bias as large as -0.41 psu with
441 respect to MEDISH in the upper layer of the Western Mediterranean (Table 2). Such
442 large negative salinity biases could indicate that the salinity restoring term might be too
443 weak to compensate for the too weak water loss simulated by ERA40 [*Mariotti et al.*,
444 2002; *Josey*, 2003]. It is also worth noting that models show very little inter-annual
445 variability compared to MEDISH, especially the ORCA model.

446 *b) Dense water formation rates*

447 In order to understand why some models reproduce sea level better than others in the
448 Mediterranean Sea it is important to analyze the driving mechanisms. One of these
449 mechanism is deep water formation, which is responsible for heat and salt vertical
450 exchanges that affect the temperature and salinity of the whole water column and hence
451 sea level. It is reasonable to assume that models that do not show deep water formation
452 in the main formation sites of the basin will not perform well either in reproducing the
453 associated sea level changes. This is particularly true for the EMT years, when an
454 increase/decrease in deep water formation was observed in the Aegean/Adriatic Sea.

455 Annual formation rates have been estimated for deep and intermediate waters in the
456 Gulf of Lions, the Adriatic and the Aegean Sea following the methodology by
457 *Lascaratós* [1993]. This methodology consists of first computing the volume of water
458 with potential density greater than a selected value. Then, for every year, the difference
459 between the maximum volume after the winter season and the minimum volume before
460 the winter season is computed and divided by the number of seconds in a year to obtain
461 the formation rate. It is important to note that the characteristics of the water masses
462 may vary between models as they have been shown to have temperature and salinity
463 biases (Section 3.1a) and, thus, using the same value of the potential density for all
464 models would not be adequate as it could lead to wrong conclusions. In order to

465 overcome this problem we used different values of the potential density for each model,
466 basing on the averaged potential density of selected layers. For deep waters we
467 computed the time-mean of the averaged potential density corresponding to the waters
468 below 2000 m; in the Eastern Mediterranean we obtained 29.13 kg/m^3 , 29.18 kg/m^3
469 and 29.18 kg/m^3 for the ORCA, OM8 and MITgcm models, respectively, while in the
470 Western Mediterranean the values are 29.05 kg/m^3 , 29.08 kg/m^3 and 29.08 kg/m^3 . The
471 minimum potential density for the formation of intermediate waters was computed as
472 the time-mean of the averaged potential density in the layer 200-500 m, obtaining 28.93
473 kg/m^3 , 28.93 kg/m^3 and 29.01 kg/m^3 for the ORCA, OM8 and MITgcm models,
474 respectively, in the Eastern Mediterranean and 28.7 kg/m^3 , 28.7 kg/m^3 and 28.8 kg/m^3
475 in the Western Mediterranean.

476 Dense water formation rates in the Gulf of Lions are shown in Fig. 2, both for deep
477 waters (Fig. 2, top) and intermediate waters (Fig. 2, bottom). The MITgcm and OM8
478 models show similar rates of both deep and intermediate water formation in this region,
479 while ORCA shows a very small rate. All models show much higher rates of
480 intermediate than deep water formation. The values of dense water formation rates
481 given by the models (0-0.9 Sv) are in the lower limit of the range reported in the
482 literature, obtained from models or in situ observations (0-2.4 Sv) [Tziperman and
483 Speer, 1994; Castellari et al., 2000; Herrmann et al., 2008; Schroeder et al., 2008]. It is
484 worth mentioning that the fact that the dense water formation rate is computed using
485 monthly averaged model results and not daily could lead to an underestimation of the
486 rates. The inter-annual variability of dense water formation shows peaks in 1963, 1971,
487 1981 and 1984, which is in good agreement with the results obtained from the
488 numerical simulations conducted by Castellari et al. [2000].

489 Fig. 3 shows the dense water formation rates computed in the Aegean Sea. The only
490 model that shows a significant deep water formation is the MITgcm (Fig. 3, top), which
491 displays high values after 1985 reaching a maximum between 1992-1993 (above 0.9 Sv)
492 and secondary maxima in 1985, 1987, 1989 and 1995 (above 0.4 Sv). For this model,
493 the average deep water formation rate for the period 1987-1993 is 0.5 Sv and 0.9 Sv for
494 the period 1992-1993. The other two models show no significant deep water formation.
495 Regarding the formation of intermediate water (Fig. 3, bottom), the MITgcm model is
496 again the one showing the largest rates (an average of 0.36 Sv for the period 1961-
497 2000), although the difference with the OM8 (0.21 Sv) is much smaller than for the
498 deep water formation. The ORCA model shows a much weaker average rate of 0.07 Sv.
499 The most prominent features are the two peaks obtained in 1983 (not shown by ORCA)
500 and during the period 1992-1993, both of them with rates larger than 0.6 Sv. If we take
501 into account both the deep and intermediate water formation, the average values of
502 dense water formation for the MITgcm (the only model showing significant deep water
503 formation) are 0.9 Sv and 1.3 Sv for 1987-1993 and 1992-1993, respectively. Validating
504 those values is rather difficult as no direct current meter measurements are available.
505 However, both the rates and their inter-annual variability shown by the MITgcm model
506 compare rather well with other studies. *Tsimplis et al.* [1999] deduced a value of 0.5 Sv
507 between October 1991 and January 1995, obtained by evaluating hydrographic data
508 using a hydraulic model. *Nittis et al.* [2003] found an average rate of 0.4 Sv for 1987-
509 1994 using a numerical model. *Rupolo et al.* [2003] also used a numerical model to find
510 an average of 0.7 Sv for 1988-1993, and 1.3 Sv for 1992-1993. The largest values were
511 found by *Roether et al.* [2007] who used repeated hydrographic and transient tracer
512 surveys to find a value of 2.8 Sv during 1992-1994.

513 Dense water formation rates in the Adriatic Sea are shown in Fig. 4. A regular
514 formation of deep water is shown by all models (Fig. 4, top). The MITgcm is again the
515 one showing larger rates, though the differences between MITgcm and the other two
516 models are smaller than in the Aegean Sea. With regard to the intermediate water
517 formation (Fig. 4, bottom), the MITgcm and OM8 models show similar overall
518 formation rates of intermediate water; while for ORCA the rate is also regular, but much
519 less intense than for the other two models. The average rates of dense water formation
520 (deep and intermediate water) for the period 1961-2000 are 0.78 Sv, 0.15 Sv and 0.42
521 Sv for the MITgcm, ORCA and OM8 models, respectively. Both regional models show
522 larger values than those reported in other studies (0.19-0.36 Sv) [*Lascarat*os, 1993;
523 *Castellari et al.*, 2000], while those from ORCA are weaker.

524 The fact that the ORCA model shows very little dense water formation as compared to
525 the regional models confirms previous findings [*Herrmann and Somot*, 2008; *Herrmann*
526 *et al.*, 2008; *Béranger et al.* 2010] that the spatial resolution of both the model and the
527 atmospheric forcing plays a crucial role in reproducing dense water formation. The
528 differences between the MITgcm and the OM8 model are probably related to the higher
529 resolution of the MITgcm atmospheric forcings and to the fact that the MITgcm uses
530 inter-annual variability for the Black Sea and the river runoff. Also the use of partial
531 bottom cell topography by the MITgcm model helps for a better representation of the
532 dense shelf water cascading, although it is a secondary source of heat in front of open
533 sea convection.

534 **3.2 Sea level variability and trends**

535 *a) Sea level variability and trends for the period 1993-2000*

536 Fig. 5 shows the distribution of sea level trends for the period 1993-2000 as obtained
537 from altimetry and the three models. The main features of the distribution of trends
538 obtained from altimetric SLA (Fig. 5a) are well reproduced by the MITgcm (Fig. 5b).
539 Indeed, it shows strong negative trends (up to -13 mm/yr) in the Ionian Sea and marked
540 positive trends in the Levantine basin, reaching a maximum value to the south of Crete
541 (20 mm/yr). The values of the positive trends obtained in the Aegean Sea are similar to
542 those shown by altimetry data; the negative trends of the Ionian Sea are only slightly
543 smaller (-3 mm/yr on average) and cover a wide part of the region, in good agreement
544 with altimetry. The main features of the distribution of sea level trends shown by
545 altimetry are related to the changes in the thermohaline circulation of the basin during
546 the post-EMT period and will be investigated more in detail in Section 3.3. The
547 agreement between MITgcm and altimetry is not as good when analysing smaller
548 structures.

549 The distribution of sea level trends obtained from the OM8 model (Fig. 5c) shows
550 significant differences with respect to altimetry. The positive trends obtained in the
551 Eastern Mediterranean are slightly smaller than those given by altimetry, but the pattern
552 is different. OM8 does neither reproduce the marked negative trends observed in the
553 Ionian Sea.

554 The trends obtained from ORCA (Fig. 5d) are markedly positive over the whole basin.
555 In the Levantine basin they are smaller than those observed with altimetry and have a
556 different pattern. In the Ionian Sea the model gives positive trends, instead of the
557 marked negative trends observed in that region. In the Western Mediterranean the
558 positive trends are stronger than those given by altimetry.

559 The steric sea level trends estimated from the three models are not presented because
560 they show a spatial pattern very similar to total sea level trends. The differences are that

561 the MITgcm and OM8 models give steric trends that are less negative than total sea
562 level trends in the Ionian Sea and slightly larger in the Aegean Sea. The differences
563 found between the total and steric sea level in the regional models are mainly caused by
564 water mass redistributions within the basin as these models do not account for mass
565 exchanges between the Atlantic and the Mediterranean. Steric sea level trends obtained
566 from ORCA are smaller than for total sea level everywhere in the basin. In this case the
567 differences between the total and steric sea level have also a contribution from the mass
568 exchange with the Atlantic.

569 The inter-annual variability of Mediterranean mean sea level (averaged over the whole
570 basin) as given by altimetry and the three models has also been examined (Fig. 6). Total
571 sea level from ORCA shows the highest correlation (0.69) with SLA from altimetry
572 (computed after detrending all time series). No significant correlation is found between
573 SLA from altimetry and that from the other two models; the variability obtained from
574 altimetry observations is clearly larger than that from MITgcm and OM8 (standard
575 deviation from altimetry doubles the standard deviation from models). This result is not
576 surprising as the total sea level from the regional models does not reflect the influence
577 of remote sea level variability (i.e., mass exchanges with the Atlantic), which has been
578 shown to be the dominant contribution to Mediterranean mean sea level at inter-annual
579 scales [Calafat *et al.*, 2010]. The fact that ORCA is the only model that accounts for the
580 mass component explains why it shows the highest correlation with the mean sea level
581 from altimetry. Concerning Mediterranean mean sea level trends, the value obtained
582 from the MITgcm is very similar to that obtained from altimetry (3% larger), while that
583 from OM8 and ORCA are 40% and 70%, respectively, larger than the altimetric one
584 (Table 4). The temporal sea level variability has also been examined for the Western
585 and Eastern Mediterranean, and the Adriatic, the Aegean and the Ionian Seas separately.

586 In particular, correlation coefficients between the regional-averaged sea level from
587 models and that from altimetry have been computed for these regions (Table 6). Again
588 the total sea level from the ORCA model shows the highest correlation with the SLA
589 from altimetry in all regions except in the Aegean Sea. Correlations for the ORCA
590 model are above 0.6 in all regions. The regional models perform really poorly in the
591 Western Mediterranean and the Ionian Sea with correlations below 0.2. In the other
592 regions, the regional models show higher correlations between 0.4 and 0.6. It is worth
593 noting that, in some areas, regional models show larger correlations for regional (sub-
594 basin) sea level than for the basin mean sea level. The reason for this is that, unlike for
595 the mean sea level, local changes due to mass redistributions within the basin can play a
596 relevant role in regional sea level. Spatial correlations have also been computed for the
597 same regions as in Table 6 but no significant correlations have been found for any of the
598 models. This was an expected result as far as the spatial patterns of sea level are
599 strongly modulated by mesoscale [Tsimplis et al., 2008] which is not properly
600 reproduced by the models (i.e. they are eddy-permitting models).

601 ***b) Sea level variability and trends for the period 1961-2000***

602 The regional distributions of sea level trends for the period 1961-2000 estimated from
603 the reconstruction and the three models are shown in Fig. 7. Sea level trends from the
604 reconstruction are positive all over the basin with values ranging between 0.7 and 1.2
605 mm/yr in the Western Mediterranean and between 0.5 and 1.7 mm/yr in the Eastern
606 Mediterranean. The largest trends are found in the Ionian Sea where they reach 2 mm/yr
607 and are associated to the EMT (see next section). The distribution estimated from the
608 MITgcm simulation (Fig. 7b) also shows positive trends almost everywhere. The most
609 prominent features are the relative maxima obtained in the Ionian Sea (up to 2 mm/yr),
610 the Western Mediterranean and the Levantine basin, while almost zero trends (about 0.5

611 mm/yr) are observed in the Aegean Sea. The positive trend found in the Ionian Sea is
612 also given by the OM8 simulation (Fig. 7c) and corresponds to a maximum in the
613 reconstructed sea level (Fig. 7a), although in the models it covers a smaller area than in
614 the reconstruction and it appears surrounded by other mesoscale structures. In the
615 Adriatic Sea the MITgcm and OM8 models show trends between 0.5 and 1 mm/yr,
616 which are also in good agreement with the reconstructed trends. In the Western
617 Mediterranean the pattern given by the OM8 model (Fig. 7c) is very similar to that of
618 MITgcm (Fig. 7b), with positive trends of up to 2.5 mm/yr. However, the reconstruction
619 presents a rather different pattern there, with trends of less than 1 mm/yr where the
620 models show the strongest trends and trends between 1.1-1.4 mm/yr elsewhere (Fig.
621 7a). The trends obtained from the ORCA simulation (Fig. 7d) are unrealistically large
622 (between 4 and 8 mm/yr) everywhere (note the different colour scales in the figure). It is
623 worth mentioning here that such large trends in ORCA have been reported to be due to
624 an overestimation of the precipitation by CORE forcings [*DRAKKAR Group, 2007*].
625 Moreover, the spatial pattern of trends in ORCA does not match the reconstruction
626 patterns.

627 We have also computed the regional trends (for the period 1961-2000) of steric sea level
628 (integrated from top to 700 m) for the three models (Fig. 8). Both the MITgcm and
629 OM8 steric distributions (Figs. 8a,b) resemble total sea level distributions (Figs. 7b,c)
630 but with values that are smaller (~0.5 mm/yr smaller). The positive peak in the Ionian
631 Sea is similar to that obtained for total sea level (up to 2 mm/yr), though it is slightly
632 weaker. When the steric sea level from the models is computed by integrating from top
633 to bottom (not shown) the distribution of steric trends is similar to that shown in Fig. 8
634 but with much larger trends (above 3 mm/yr) in the Western Mediterranean. These
635 unrealistic large trends in the Western subbasin seem to be a recurrent problem in all

636 regional simulations, originated by the warming drift in the deepest layers of the
637 subbasin reported above. The steric trends derived from the ORCA model (Fig. 8c) do
638 not resemble the corresponding total sea level trends (Fig. 7d), denoting the influence of
639 the mass component on sea level evolution in the ORCA model. The values of the steric
640 trends are smaller than total sea level trends and actually more realistic everywhere in
641 the basin, although it also shows large unrealistic positive trends in the Western
642 Mediterranean due to the warming of the deeper layers.

643 Concerning the inter-annual variability, correlation coefficients between the regional-
644 averaged sea level from models and that from reconstruction have been computed for
645 different areas for the period 1950-2000 (Table 6). The obtained values are smaller than
646 during the altimetric period. Total sea level from the ORCA model shows the highest
647 correlation with the reconstruction in all regions (0.4-0.6) except in the Ionian Sea. The
648 regional models also perform poorly in the Western Mediterranean and the Ionian Sea
649 with non-significant correlations.

650 The mean sea level averaged over the whole Mediterranean Sea has also been computed
651 for the period 1961-2000. Fig. 9 (top) shows the yearly total sea level time series
652 obtained from the reconstruction and the MITgcm and OM8 models. Mean sea level
653 from ORCA is not shown because its large trend (see Table 4) requires a change in the
654 scale of the figure that prevents a clear interpretation of the other curves. Conversely,
655 the mean sea level trends obtained from the MITgcm and OM8 models are similar to
656 that obtained from the reconstruction (Table 4). In terms of variability (after detrending
657 the time series), the only model showing a significant correlation (0.5) with the
658 reconstruction is ORCA (Table 5). As for the altimetric period, all models show a
659 smoother variability than the observed (reconstructed) sea level (standard deviation
660 from modelled time series being about half of the standard deviation of the

661 reconstructed time series). As for the altimetric period, the temporal sea level variability
662 has also been examined for the Western and Eastern Mediterranean, and the Adriatic,
663 the Aegean and the Ionian Seas. Correlation coefficients between the regional-averaged
664 sea level from models and that from the reconstruction are summarized in Table 6. Total
665 sea level from the ORCA model shows the highest correlation with sea level from the
666 reconstruction in both the Western (0.4) and Eastern (0.5) Mediterranean. None of the
667 regional models show significant correlations in the Western Mediterranean. In the
668 Ionian Sea the highest correlation (0.3) is found for the MITgcm. The other two models
669 do not show significant correlation in this region. In the Adriatic and Aegean Sea all
670 models show similar correlations (between 0.4 and 0.6).

671 The mean steric sea level for the upper 700 m has also been computed from the
672 MEDISH data base and the three models (Fig. 9, bottom). Correlations between the
673 steric sea level estimated from MEDISH and from models are significant in all cases,
674 the highest value (0.7) being that of OM8 (Table 5). However none of the models
675 reproduce the trend of the steric component of mean sea level obtained from MEDISH
676 data: MITgcm, ORCA and OM8 show positive steric trends (0.6, 1.1 and 0.5 mm/yr,
677 respectively) while the steric trend obtained from MEDISH is negative (-0.4 mm/yr).

678 **3.3 The Eastern Mediterranean Transient**

679 The EMT was responsible for one of the most energetic signals in sea level variability
680 in the last decades. Thus, it seems worth investigating if the different models are able to
681 reproduce that signal and trying to elucidate the reason of their performance. Several
682 authors have attempted to reproduce the processes involved in the EMT by means of
683 numerical simulations. *Lascaratós et al.* [1999] combined a review of hydrological
684 observations and numerical simulations to conclude that the intensity of the atmospheric
685 forcing (both the heat and fresh water fluxes) is a major factor in the formation of dense

686 water in the Aegean Sea. Numerical studies carried out by *Stratford and Haines* [2002]
687 showed that the role of the wind is secondary to the role of buoyancy forcing and that
688 the cooling occurred during the winters of 1987, 1992 and 1993 can trigger the
689 formation of deep water. *Nittis et al.* [2003] not only pointed to the very cold winters of
690 1987, 1992 and 1993, but also to the dry period 1989-1993 that affected the whole
691 Eastern Mediterranean as the main driving mechanisms, being responsible for 50% and
692 32%, respectively, of the deep water formed in the Aegean after 1987. The reduced
693 Black Sea Water outflow observed during the same dry period accounted for a 18% of
694 the total formation, while the increase inflow of saline waters from the Levantine Sea
695 after 1992 is recognized as an additional preconditioning factor. Finally, the numerical
696 study of *Beuvier et al.* [2010] has shown that changes in the circulation in the Eastern
697 Mediterranean could play a role in the preconditioning of the EMT. Also, they
698 concluded that all the preconditioning factors mentioned above increased the salinity in
699 the Aegean but that the key triggering elements of the EMT were the surface heat and
700 water losses which occurred during the severe winters 1991–1992 and 1992–1993.

701

702 In Section 3.1 it has been shown that the MITgcm model is the only one showing deep
703 water formation in the Aegean Sea during the EMT period. For a better assessment of
704 the dense water formation mechanisms, water properties such as temperature, salinity
705 and potential density, have been annually averaged in the Aegean Sea for the period
706 1961-2000. As in Section 3.1, the averages have been computed for the layers 0-100 m,
707 100-500 m, 500-1000 m and 1000-2000 m (Fig. 10).

708 *Lascaratos et al.* [1999] showed that the waters located at about 1000 m depth in the
709 Cretan Sea increased their density about 0.17 kg/m^3 during the period 1987-1995. The
710 MITgcm model shows a pronounced density increase in the layers 100-500 m (+ 0.15

711 kg/m³) and 500-1000 m (+0.07 kg/m³) during that period, with a maximum peak in
712 1993 (Fig. 10c). The OM8 model also shows a density increase and a peak in 1993 in
713 the layer 100-500 m (+0.1 kg/m³), but they do not reflect in the layer 500-1000 m. The
714 ORCA model only shows a small peak in the density of the layer 100-500 m in 1993.

715 Observations suggest that the increase in the density was first due to a salinity increase
716 occurred during the period 1987-1992 and, later (1992-1995), to a decrease in
717 temperature [Lascaratos *et al.*, 1999]. This behaviour is reproduced by the MITgcm
718 model, which shows both, a salinity increase throughout the whole water column from
719 1986 to 1992 and a decrease in the temperature of the top 1000 m during the years
720 1992-1993. The other two models also show the decrease in temperature, but they do
721 not show any salinity increase for the period 1987-1992. According to the hypothesis of
722 Nittis *et al.* [2003], this would explain why the MITgcm model is the only one showing
723 deep water formation in the Aegean Sea, while the other two models only show
724 intermediate water formation in this area. Moreover, the MITgcm model reproduces the
725 increased water formation rates not only during the cold winters of 1987 and 1992-1993
726 but also during the period in between, characterized by relatively mild winters. This is
727 in good agreement with the results based on observations shown by Theocharis *et al.*
728 [1999] and with the numerical simulation carried out by Nittis *et al.* [2003] and should
729 be attributed to the preconditioning of the 1987 winter and to the increased buoyancy
730 loss due to the freshwater anomaly observed during the period 1989-1990.

731 In Section 3.2 it has been shown that changes in the thermohaline circulation of the
732 basin during the post-EMT period were clearly reflected on regional sea level changes
733 such as the sea level decrease observed in the Ionian Sea and the strong sea level
734 increase observed in the Aegean Sea during the altimetric period 1993-2000 (see Fig.
735 5a). In order to see if the MITgcm and OM8 models show the same behaviour we have

736 averaged the sea level fields given by the two models and the reconstruction over the
737 Aegean Sea and over the Ionian Sea for the period 1961-2000 (Fig. 11). Again, the time
738 series from ORCA is not shown because its trend is so large as compared to the other
739 time series that the scale of the figure should be expanded. We have also computed the
740 regionally averaged sea level variability from the three models and from altimetric data
741 for the period 1993-2000 (not shown). The correlation coefficients as well as the linear
742 trends obtained for the periods 1993-2000 and 1961-2000 are listed in Tables 6 and 7,
743 respectively.

744 In the Aegean Sea (Fig. 11a), the total sea level from all models is well correlated
745 (between 0.4 and 0.6) with that from the reconstruction for the period 1961-2000.
746 Although, only the regional simulations reproduce the sea level drop during the years
747 1985-1993 (though the drop is deeper in the reconstruction) and the subsequent rebound
748 after 1993. With regard to trends for the shorter period, all models show large positive
749 values that are similar to the altimetric trends, though the MITgcm trend is the closest
750 one to altimetry (Table 7). For the period 1961-2000 only the trend from the MITgcm is
751 in good agreement with that from the reconstruction. The trend derived from the ORCA
752 model is unrealistically large (Table 7).

753 In the Ionian Sea the situation is rather different. For the period 1961-2000 both the
754 MITgcm and OM8 models show trends that are close to the reconstruction and ORCA
755 shows again unrealistic trends (Table 7), despite only the MITgcm total sea level is well
756 correlated with the reconstructed sea level (0.6). The MITgcm model reproduces the sea
757 level jump shown by the reconstruction during the major part of the EMT (1987-1992)
758 and the subsequent sea level drop after 1992. These features are not well captured by the
759 other two models; in particular, the only model showing large negative trends for the
760 period 1993-2000 is the MITgcm model, with values that are in good agreement with

761 the altimetric and the reconstructed trends (Table 7). Again the ORCA model is the one
762 performing poorer in terms of sea level trends, showing an unreliable large positive
763 trend for the period 1961-2000. For the period 1993-2000 ORCA shows a positive trend
764 in opposition to the large negative trend shown by altimetry (Table 7), although it is the
765 model showing the largest correlation with the observations for that period (Table 6).

766 It is important to note that only the regional models are capable of reproducing the main
767 sea level features during the EMT and post-EMT periods in the Ionian and the Aegean.
768 These sea level changes are clearly linked to the changes in the thermohaline circulation
769 occurring during those periods and, thus, reproducing the processes driving such
770 changes is crucial to capture the sea level variability in those regions. It has been
771 recently shown by *Herrmann et al.* [2009] that there is a strong correlation between
772 dense water formation and the sea level in the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea. We
773 have computed the correlation between the total sea level and the deep water formation
774 rates for the three models in the Aegean Sea. For the MITgcm model we find a
775 correlation of -0.7, while that for the OM8 model is -0.6. No significant correlation is
776 found for the ORCA model. The fact that there is such large correlation between dense
777 water formation and sea level explains why the MITgcm is the model that performs
778 better in reproducing the main features during the EMT and post-EMT periods. The
779 OM8 model, which does not properly reproduce the EMT, is only significantly
780 correlated with the reconstruction in the Aegean. In Section 3.1d it has been shown that
781 the MITgcm is the model showing the highest rates of deep water formation in both the
782 Aegean and Ionian Seas. This explains why the MITgcm and the OM8 perform better
783 than the ORCA model and indicates that the resolution of both the model and the
784 atmospheric forcing are crucial to reproduce regional sea level, especially in regions

785 affected by intense mesoscale processes. The fact that the MITgcm and the OM8 are not
786 eddy-resolving partly explains why they do not exactly reproduce those processes.

787 In summary, the only model that shows a density increase below 500 m in the Aegean
788 Sea during the EMT period (1987-1995) is the MITgcm. The reason is that only
789 MITgcm reproduces the salinity increase during the period 1987-1992, which was a key
790 process in the evolution of the EMT. Regarding sea level, all models show significant
791 correlations (between 0.4 and 0.6) with both the SLA from altimetry (1993-2000) and
792 the sea level from the reconstruction (1961-2000) in the Aegean although only MITgcm
793 shows significant correlation with observations in the Ionian.

794

795 **4. Summary and Discussion**

796 At inter-annual scales, of the three hindcasts analyzed in this work only the
797 Mediterranean mean sea level given by the ORCA model is significantly correlated with
798 altimetry data (for the period 1993-2000) and with the sea level reconstruction obtained
799 by *Calafat and Gomis* [2009] (for the period 1961-2000). The sea level variability of the
800 MITgcm and OM8 models is significantly smoother than the observed one. The most
801 likely probable reason is that in the regional models, the water mass exchange between
802 the Atlantic and the Mediterranean is limited by the imposition of a fixed sea level
803 height at the Atlantic boundary, a restriction that does not affect global models such as
804 ORCA. *Calafat et al.* [2010] have actually shown that the inter-annual variability of sea
805 level in the Mediterranean is largely dominated by mass changes, which would explain
806 why total sea level from the MITgcm and OM8 models is much smoother than observed
807 sea level.

808 With respect to mean sea level trends, both the MITgcm and the OM8 models give
809 results that are in good agreement with the reconstruction for the period 1961-2000.
810 However, since regional models do not account for water mass increases/decreases due
811 to remote sources (i.e., water redistribution within the Atlantic Ocean and continental
812 ice melting), modelled and observed trends should only be equal if the trend of the mass
813 component were negligible. *Calafat et al.* [2010] have shown that this is not the case, as
814 they found that the mass component (estimated in 1.2 mm/yr for the period 1961-2000)
815 has been the dominant of Mediterranean mean sea level trends. This indicates the
816 presence of a spurious positive trend in the steric component of sea level computed
817 from the MITgcm and OM8 models. Indeed, while all models give significant
818 correlation with the steric sea level from MEDISH data, the respective steric trends have
819 opposite sign (positive for the models and negative for MEDISH) for the period 1961-
820 2000. The case of ORCA is completely different. The reason why it shows a much
821 larger trend than the reconstruction is a large trend in Atlantic sea level (6.4 mm/yr) that
822 leads to an increase in the net water flux from the Atlantic to the Mediterranean Sea.
823 That Atlantic trend is much larger than the observed trend (1.5-2.0 mm/yr; Church et
824 al., 2004). The drift in sea surface height exhibited by the ORCA simulation has been
825 reported to be due to an overestimation of the precipitation by CORE forcings
826 [*DRAKKAR Group*, 2007].

827 The spatial distributions of the total and steric sea level trends within the basin have also
828 been studied. For the altimetric period, the MITgcm model is the only one that
829 successfully reproduces the major spatial features that characterize the altimetry data set
830 during the post-EMT period: marked negative and positive trends in the Ionian Sea and
831 in the Aegean Sea, respectively. Conversely, the MITgcm simulation is unable to
832 capture other features shown by altimetry data. For the whole period 1961-2000, all

833 models show large sea level trends in the Western Mediterranean due to the spurious
834 warming drift in the deeper layers reported above. Another major feature of this period
835 is the positive maximum obtained in the Ionian Sea, shown by the reconstruction and
836 reproduced by the MITgcm and OM8 models. The ORCA model shows large
837 unrealistic regional sea level trends everywhere in the basin.

838 In order to identify the causes of the differences between observations and the three
839 models, but also among the models themselves, we have also examined the variability
840 of the water mass properties. The analysis has been carried out averaging the values
841 over the Eastern and the Western basins on four different layers: 0-100 m, 100-500 m,
842 500-1000 m and 1000-2000 m. For the top 1000 m in the Western Mediterranean and
843 the top 500 m in the Eastern Mediterranean, averaged temperatures from all models are
844 well correlated with MEDISH. For the layer 500-1000 m in the Eastern Mediterranean
845 only the averaged temperature from the MITgcm model is significantly correlated with
846 that from MEDISH. At deeper layers models do not show significant correlations with
847 MEDISH. With regard to salinity, regional models only show significant correlations
848 with MEDISH in the upper 100m of the Western Mediterranean. None of the models
849 show significant correlations in the Eastern Mediterranean. However, it is worth
850 mentioning that observations become scarcer at deeper layers (especially for salinity),
851 so that the estimated basin averaged properties may not be representative. The time-
852 mean properties show temperature and salinity biases between observations and models
853 in some layers, although they are rather small in most cases.

854 As a complementary test, we have also examined deep water formation in the main sites
855 (the Gulf of Lions, the Adriatic and the Aegean Sea). The ORCA model presents very
856 low rates of dense water formation in all regions. In the Gulf of Lions, the OM8 and
857 MITgcm models show similar rates, but they are smaller than those reported in the

858 literature. Most of the dense water formation shown by the models in this region is in
859 the form of intermediate water. In the Adriatic, the OM8 rates are about as half of those
860 of the MITgcm. In this region, both regional models show larger values than those
861 reported in other studies, while the ORCA model shows smaller values. Finally, in the
862 Aegean Sea, only the MITgcm model shows significant deep water formation with
863 maximum values during the EMT period (1987-1993). This also explains why only this
864 model performs well in reproducing the post-EMT sea level features. The difficulty of
865 the other models to reproduce the EMT event is probably related to the use of
866 climatological values for the Black Sea and river runoff [*Beuvier et al.*, 2010], although
867 a wrong preconditioning may also limit the dense water formation. In the ORCA model,
868 also the low resolution of the model and of the atmospheric forcing used in the
869 simulation is likely to play a limiting role. Indeed, previous works [*Herrmann and*
870 *Somot*, 2008; *Herrmann et al.*, 2008] have shown that a high resolution is crucial for the
871 modelling of dense water formation, to the point that it can increase the formation rates
872 by an order of magnitude. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that an increase in the
873 spatial resolution of the models (i.e. being eddy-resolving) would probably improve the
874 representation of the deep convection processes.

875 One of the most noticeable features, which is moreover common to all models, is the
876 warming drift shown at intermediate and deep layers. The causes of the drift have been
877 investigated by studying the heat budget of the three models. Under the assumption of
878 incompressibility, the heat balance equation can be written as

$$879 \quad \iiint_V \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} dV = - \iint_S T v_{\perp} dS - \frac{HF_{Surf}}{C_p \rho} \quad (6)$$

880 where T is the potential temperature, C_p is the specific heat at atmospheric pressure,
881 ρ is the density, v_{\perp} is the velocity component perpendicular to the lateral boundaries

882 (of area S) confining the volume V , and HF_{surf} is the heat flux through the air-sea
883 interface. The term on the left-hand side represents the time change in the heat content
884 of the basin. The second term on the right-hand side accounts for the surface heat
885 sources and the area integral (first term) on the right-hand side represents the heat
886 advection in or out of the basin. In practice, this term includes the heat advected through
887 the Gibraltar and the Dardanelles straits and the heat loss associated with the mass
888 loss/gain through the surface (i.e. due to evaporation/precipitation).

889 The different components of the time-mean heat budget for the three simulations are
890 summarized in Table 8. The time-mean heat flux entering the Mediterranean Sea
891 through the Gibraltar Strait is very similar for the three models: it ranges from 4.2 to 4.5
892 W/m^2 , with a variability of less than $0.8 W/m^2$. These values are slightly smaller than
893 those reported in the literature, which range from 5 to $7 W/m^2$ [Garret *et al.*, 1993;
894 McDonald *et al.*, 1994]. For the time-mean surface heat flux we obtain values of -
895 2.7 ± 4.8 , 0.0 ± 3.3 and $-3.4 \pm 3.9 W/m^2$ for the MITgcm, ORCA and OM8 models, while
896 those given in the literature are of the order of $-7 W/m^2$ [Bethoux, 1979; Bunker *et al.*,
897 1982]. The contribution to the heat budget of the water advected through the Dardanelles
898 Strait is only considered in ORCA ($0.4 W/m^2$). Also ORCA is the only model which
899 loses heat through mass loss at surface ($-3.2 W/m^2$) as far as it is the only model which
900 represents the evaporation as a mass loss (i.e. the other models represent evaporation as
901 a virtual salt flux).

902 The most remarkable result is that all models show an imbalance between surface and
903 lateral heat fluxes. According to equation (6), that imbalance would imply an increase in
904 the heat content of the basin (i.e. a positive drift in the temperature). For the
905 Mediterranean basin, a constant heat excess of $1-1.7 W/m^2$ would represent a trend of

906 5.4-9.2 10^{-3} °C/yr (0.2-0.3°C in 40 years) for the basin averaged temperature, which is
907 consistent with the observed behaviour of the models (Table 8).

908 Identifying the ultimate causes of the imbalance is not easy, however. On one hand, the
909 Gibraltar heat exchange is determined by the temperatures of the inflow and the outflow
910 and by the flows themselves. These in turn depend on the density difference between
911 Atlantic and Mediterranean waters [*Armi and Farmer, 1988; Farmer and Armi, 1988*].
912 As all the models are initialized from the same database (MEDAR/MEDATLAS), the
913 characteristics of the inflow/outflow at Gibraltar are also very similar for all the models
914 (Table 8). However, the few observational estimates that are available indicate larger
915 values than the modelled ones [*Garret et al., 1993; Mcdonald et al., 1994*]. On the other
916 hand, surface heat fluxes are difficult to estimate with enough accuracy. *Sánchez-Gómez*
917 *et al.* [2011] have analysed the heat fluxes from an ensemble of atmospheric models and
918 shown large discrepancies among them. In fact, the model spreading is much larger than
919 the estimated value: the ensemble mean value for the net heat flux is -7 ± 21 W/m².

920 An important point to note is that the Mediterranean system will evolve in the sense of
921 reducing the imbalance in the heat fluxes until a new equilibrium state is reached. With
922 a net heat input into the system (i.e. heat loss through surface lower than heat gain
923 through Gibraltar), the inner temperature will increase. Therefore, the temperature of the
924 outflow would also increase, then increasing the heat outflow through Gibraltar. In
925 consequence, the net heat inflow through Gibraltar would decrease until it balances the
926 surface heat flux. Translating this mechanism to the model simulations, a long enough
927 spin-up should solve the imbalance problem. In order to determine the evolution of the
928 system we have analyzed the time series of the net surface heat flux (Fig. 12, top), the
929 Gibraltar Strait net heat transport (Fig. 12, middle) and the total heat budget (Fig. 12,
930 bottom) for the three models. The OM8 and ORCA models show a rapid decrease in the

931 net heat transport across Gibraltar during the first 20 years. This decrease is more
932 pronounced for ORCA, probably because no spin-up is performed in this simulation
933 and, thus, it presents a larger initial imbalance. Conversely, the MITgcm simulation
934 shows a weaker decrease in the net heat transport probably because it starts from a more
935 stable state as it uses the longest spin-up period among the three models. Results show
936 that this adjustment is mainly achieved by a reduction of both the inflow and outflow
937 volume transports at the Gibraltar Strait and it is partly offset by a decrease in the
938 temperature of the Mediterranean outflow waters (not shown here). A decrease in the
939 heat content of the waters in the upper 300 m is also shown by all models during the
940 first 20 years. Most of the heat entering the basin is transferred to deeper layers, whose
941 waters increase their temperature throughout this period. However, although the
942 imbalance is reduced, the period covered by the models is too short as to reach a new
943 equilibrium state and the total heat flux remains positive during most of the period.
944 Moreover, the last 20 years are characterized by a reduction in surface heat loss, which
945 leads to an even larger imbalance. Summarizing, it seems that a longer spin-up could
946 improve the initial conditions of the models, leading to a situation closer to the
947 equilibrium. However, the time scales required to compensate the imbalance maybe
948 much longer than the simulation period as far as it concerns the adjustment of
949 temperature at intermediate and deep layers.

950 A way to reduce the required spin-up period could be to use heat flux datasets that were
951 consistent between them or, at least, to apply a correction factor to ensure the balance.
952 The use of MEDAR/MEDATLAS to initialize the models leads to a heat flux at
953 Gibraltar of around 4.5 W/m^2 , while the ERA40 reanalysis (or the dynamical
954 downscallings from it) leads to smaller values (Table 8). Thus, a simple proposal would
955 be to correct surface heat fluxes in order to ensure that their long-term average matches

956 the heat fluxes through Gibraltar. Other proposals acting on model parameterizations
957 could also be envisaged. For instance, *Bryan* [1984] has proposed to modify the vertical
958 mixing parameterization at the deeper layers in order to accelerate convergence.

959 Finally, it is worth commenting that the three hindcasts analysed here used different
960 numerical codes and physical parameterizations. However, in the present state of
961 development, those differences seem to be of second order of importance when
962 evaluating the quality of the hindcasts. The model configuration (e.g. spatial resolution
963 or spin up procedure) or the forcings characteristics (i.e. spatial resolution of
964 atmospheric fluxes, inter-annual variability in the rivers runoff) seems to have a larger
965 impact on the model evolution.

966

967 **5. Final remarks**

968 Three hindcasts of the Mediterranean Sea spanning the period 1961-2000 and generated
969 with different baroclinic models have been analysed paying particular attention to sea
970 level. The models are a global model (ORCA), a regional forced model (OM8) and a
971 regional coupled model (MITgcm). The Mediterranean sea level variability can be
972 decomposed into the contribution of mass variations, which are mainly due to Atlantic
973 sea level variability and dominates at inter-annual scales, and local changes in density,
974 which affect the steric component of sea level and determine the spatial patterns of
975 variability within the basin. Regarding the mass component, it can only be partially
976 modelled by the global model (ORCA), because the two regional models impose a fixed
977 sea level at the Atlantic boundaries. In consequence, the inter-annual sea level
978 variability from ORCA is the only significantly correlated with observations among the

979 three models. However, its long-term trend of the mass component is largely
980 overestimated.

981 Concerning the steric component, we have analyzed the temporal evolution of
982 temperature and salinity given by the three models. The temperature variability is
983 reasonably good for the upper 1000 m but not below, where the models are smoother
984 than observations. Moreover, at intermediate and deeper layers all models show a
985 spurious warming trend, especially in the Western Mediterranean. That drift is due to an
986 imbalance between surface and lateral heat fluxes. In particular, all models show an
987 average surface heat loss smaller (in absolute value) than the net heat gain through
988 Gibraltar. A consequence of the warming drift is that long-term steric trends are
989 overestimated by all models. The salinity inter-annual variability is not satisfactory at
990 any layer, probably due to wrong surface freshwater fluxes, which are affected by large
991 uncertainties (e.g. limited spatial and temporal coverage of available observations).
992 Water mass properties are also directly related to processes of dense water formation.
993 Dense water formation rates are very different among models. The model generating the
994 largest amount is the MITgcm model, while ORCA rates are very small. The high
995 spatial resolution of the model and of the forcings along with realistic inter-annual
996 variability of freshwater sources would explain the success of the MITgcm model to
997 reproduce dense water formation. In particular, the MITgcm model is the only
998 reproducing the EMT. At subbasin scale the performance of all models is rather poor.
999 Only events with a strong signature in sea surface elevation such as the EMT are
1000 reproduced by the models in terms of regional sea level patterns and trends.

1001

1002 From the results shown in this paper, we can conclude that regional high resolution
1003 models forced by high resolution atmospheric fields are required to properly reproduce

1004 regional sea level variability processes such as the EMT. However, they must also
1005 improve the representation of the open boundary conditions in the Atlantic, in order to
1006 account for mass exchanges between the Mediterranean basin and the open ocean. Also,
1007 the imbalance in the heat forcing must be solved in order to avoid the warming drifts
1008 that contaminate the steric contribution to long-term sea level trends. Finally, a
1009 reduction of the salinity biases and an improved representation of the salinity variability
1010 are also of importance to better reproduce dense water formation and sea level
1011 variability processes. Summarizing, recent improvements in Mediterranean Sea
1012 modelling are encouraging, but a long way is still required to correctly reproduce the
1013 complexity of the Mediterranean Sea climate at regional and local scales. This is a
1014 particularly sensitive issue for the projection of regional future climate scenarios and
1015 confidence on projections will increase as models skills will be improved.

1016

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1273 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

1274 **Figure 1.** Detrended annual time series of temperature and salinity anomalies over the
1275 period 1961-2000 averaged over the Eastern Mediterranean (a,c) and the Western
1276 Mediterranean (b,d) for four different layers: 0-100 m, 100-500 m, 500-1000 m and
1277 1000-2000 m. They have been estimated from the MEDISH database (green line) and
1278 from the three models: MITgcm (blue line), and OM8 (black line) and ORCA (dashed-
1279 dotted line).

1280 **Figure 2.** Annual time series of dense water formation rates (Sv) in the Gulf of Lions as
1281 obtained from the MITgcm (blue line), ORCA (dashed-dotted line) and OM8 (black
1282 line) models. The formation rates have been estimated for deep (>2000 m) water (top)
1283 and intermediate (200-500 m) water (bottom).

1284 **Figure 3.** Same as Figure 2 but for the Aegean Sea.

1285 **Figure 4.** Same as Figure 2 but for the Adriatic Sea.

1286 **Figure 5.** Distribution of total sea level trends for the period 1993-2000 as obtained
1287 from: a) altimetric SLA; b) the MITgcm model; c) the OM8 model; and d) the ORCA
1288 model. The black contour level indicates the 0 value. Units are mm/yr.

1289 **Figure 6.** Monthly time series of Mediterranean mean sea level for the period 1993-
1290 2000 estimated from altimetry data and the MITgcm, ORCA and OM8 models. A
1291 centered 12-months moving average has been applied to all time series.

1292 **Figure 7.** Distribution of total sea level trends for the period 1961-2000 as obtained
1293 from: a) the sea level reconstruction by *Calafat and Gomis* [2009]; b) the MITgcm
1294 model; c) the OM8 model; and d) the ORCA model. The black contour level indicates
1295 the 0 value Units are mm/yr.

1296 **Figure 8.** Distribution of steric sea level (integrated from top to 700 m) trends for the
1297 period 1961-2000 as obtained from: a) the MITgcm model; b) the OM8 model and c)
1298 the ORCA model. Units are mm/yr in all cases.

1299 **Figure 9.** Monthly time series for the period 1961-2000 of: a) Mediterranean mean sea
1300 level estimated from the reconstruction, and the MITgcm and OM8 and b) steric
1301 component of mean sea level for the top 700 m estimated from the MITgcm, ORCA and
1302 OM8 models and the MEDISH database (with errors bars). A centered 12-months
1303 moving average has been applied to all time series.

1304 **Figure 10.** Annual time series of averaged temperature (a), salinity (b) and potential
1305 density (c) in the Aegean Sea over the period 1961-2000 for the layers 0-100 m, 100-
1306 500 m, 500-1000 m and 1000-2000 m as given by the MITgcm (blue line), ORCA
1307 (dashed-dotted line) and OM8 (black line). The EMT period has been highlighted in
1308 gray.

1309 **Figure 11.** Monthly regional-averaged total sea level for the period 1961-2000
1310 estimated from the reconstruction (thick black line) and the MITgcm (blue line) and
1311 OM8 (thin black line) models averaged over: (a) the Aegean Sea; (b) the Ionian Sea. A
1312 centered 12-months moving average has been applied to all time series. Both the EMT
1313 and post-EMT periods have been highlighted in gray.

1314 **Figure 12.** Yearly averaged time series of the net surface heat flux (top), the net heat
1315 transport at the Gibraltar Strait (middle) and the total heat flux (sum of the other two)
1316 (bottom). Note that values are normalized by the surface of the Mediterranean area to be
1317 consistent with the surface flux. A centered 6-years moving average has been applied to
1318 all time series.

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1322 **Table 1.** Summary of models characteristics.

Model	Horizontal Resolution	Atmospheric forcing	Forcing at Atlantic boundary	SSS relaxation	River forcing
ORCA	1/4° x 1/4°	Forced by ERA40 (~125 km/ 6 hours)	Inter-annual variability	Yes (60 days)	Climatology
OM8	1/8° x 1/8° cos(<i>lat</i>)	Forced by ARPERA (~50km/ 24 hours)	Seasonal climatology	No	Climatology
MITgcm	1/8° x 1/8°	Coupled to RegCM3 (~30km/6 hours)	Seasonal climatology	No	Interactive river scheme

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1326 **Table 2.** Bias between the basin mean temperature and salinity given by the models and
 1327 MEDISH. They have been computed for the Western and Eastern basins for the period
 1328 1961-2000.

TEMPERATURE BIAS [°C]						
Layer	Western Mediterranean			Eastern Mediterranean		
	MITgmc	ORCA	OM8	MITgmc	ORCA	OM8
0-100	-0.50	0.46	0.37	-0.83	0.39	0.12
100-500	-0.01	0.82	0.67	-0.07	0.37	0.48
500-1000	0.23	0.33	0.63	0.18	0.04	0.33
1000-2000	0.01	0.05	-0.08	-0.02	0.12	-0.13

SALINITY BIAS [psu]						
Layer	Western Mediterranean			Eastern Mediterranean		
	MITgmc	ORCA	OM8	MITgmc	ORCA	OM8
0-100	-0.083	-0.410	-0.164	0.105	-0.130	0.046
100-500	-0.063	-0.002	0.022	0.068	0.033	0.084
500-1000	0.020	0.013	0.058	0.035	-0.043	0.017
1000-2000	0.035	0.006	0.012	0.040	0.018	-0.013

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1333 **Table 3.** Linear trends and their associated uncertainty (computed with a robust
1334 bootstrap) for the basin mean temperature and salinity estimated from the models and
1335 from MEDISH. They have been computed for the Western and Eastern Mediterranean
1336 basins over the period 1961-2000.

TEMPERATURE				
WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN [10^{-3} °C/year]				
Layer	0-100	100-500	500-1000	1000-2000
MEDAR	7.8±2.5	-0.3±1.2	2.2±0.5	2.7±0.2
ORCA	0.2±2.9	8.1±1.2	13.2±0.6	0.6±0.1
OM8	8.3±2.2	5.8±1.1	12.9±0.8	6.2±0.1
MITgcm	6.0±2.6	4.1±1.2	8.0±0.6	9.7±0.4
EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN [10^{-3} °C/year]				
Layer	0-100	100-500	500-1000	1000-2000
MEDAR	-0.5±2.8	-6.7±1.3	-0.3±0.4	0.5±0.3
ORCA	0.0±2.3	3.3±0.8	3.5±0.1	0.2±0.4
OM8	0.3±3.0	-3.8±1.1	6.0±0.3	4.4±0.1
MITgcm	1.4±2.8	-2.4±1.5	3.7±0.5	6.7±0.2
SALINITY				
WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN [10^{-3} psu/year]				
Layer	0-100	100-500	500-1000	1000-2000
MEDAR	0.3±0.8	1.9±0.6	1.1±0.2	1.1±0.1
ORCA	-1.8±0.3	-1.2±0.3	1.2±0.1	0.1±0.1
OM8	-0.8±0.5	0.4±0.2	0.9±0.1	0.4±0.1
MITgcm	-1.7±0.6	-1.1±0.6	0.6±0.2	1.4±0.1
EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN [10^{-3} psu/year]				
Layer	0-100	100-500	500-1000	1000-2000
MEDAR	-2.7±0.5	-0.5±0.3	0.2±0.3	0.4±0.4
ORCA	-0.2±0.3	-0.9±0.1	-0.1±0.1	0.0±0.1
OM8	-2.8±0.4	1.7±0.2	0.5±0.1	0.7±0.1
MITgcm	-2.2±0.6	-4.3±0.2	0.3±0.2	0.6±0.1

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1338 **Table 4.** Mean sea level trends for the periods 1993-2000 and 1961-2000 estimated
1339 from altimetry and reconstructed sea level fields and from three numerical models.

MEAN SEA LEVEL TRENDS [mm/yr]		
	1993-2000	1961-2000
Altimetry	3.8±0.4	-
Reconstruction	4.1±0.4	1.0±0.1
ORCA	6.4±0.7	6.1±0.2
OM8	5.4±0.2	1.1±0.1
MITgcm	3.9±0.2	1.2±0.1

1340 **Table 5.** Correlation between the modelled and the reconstructed mean sea level, and
 1341 between the steric sea level obtained from the models and MEDISH, for the period
 1342 1961-2000. NS stands for non-significant correlation. All time series have been
 1343 detrended prior the the computation of the correlations.

Correlation for the period 1961-2000		
	Total sea level (Reconstruction)	Steric (MEDISH)
ORCA	0.5	0.4
OM8	NS	0.7
MITgcm	NS	0.4

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1347 **Table 6.** Correlation between the regional-averaged sea level from the models and that
 1348 from altimetry (1993-2000) and the reconstruction (1961-2000) by *Calafat and Gomis*
 1349 [2009]. They have been computed for the Western and Eastern Mediterranean, and the
 1350 Adriatic, Aegean and Ionian Seas. All time series have been detrended prior the the
 1351 computation of the correlations. NS stands for non-significant correlation.

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Correlation for the period 1993-2000/1961-2000					
	WMED	EMED	Adriatic	Aegean	Ionian
ORCA	0.7 / 0.4	0.7 / 0.5	0.7 / 0.5	0.6 / 0.6	0.8 / NS
OM8	0.2 / NS	0.5 / 0.3	0.4 / 0.5	0.6 / 0.5	NS / NS
MITgcm	NS / NS	0.5 / 0.3	0.4 / 0.4	0.6 / 0.4	0.2 / 0.3

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1356 **Table 7.** Total sea level trends in the Aegean and Ionian seas for the periods 1993-2000
 1357 and 1961-2000 estimated from the three models, the sea level reconstruction of *Calafat*
 1358 *and Gomis* [2009], and altimetry.

TOTAL SEA LEVEL TRENDS [mm/yr]				
	Aegean Sea		Ionian Sea	
Period	1993-2000	1961-2000	1993-2000	1961-2000
Altimetry	10.7±0.5	-	-11.7±1.2	-
Reconstruction	9.8±0.4	0.6±0.1	-9.1±1.0	1.8±0.1
MITgcm	9.5±0.5	0.6±0.1	-11.7±1.3	1.7±0.1
ORCA	7.3±0.6	5.9±0.2	7.7±0.8	5.9±0.2
OM8	8.9±0.7	0.9±0.1	-2.3±0.9	1.7±0.1

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1361 **Table 8.** Time-mean heat budget for the MITgcm, ORCA and OM8 models over
 1362 the Mediterranean basin for the period 1961-2000 (in W/m²). ΔQ is the change in
 1363 heat content over that period computed from model temperature fields. Note that
 1364 values are normalized by the surface of the Mediterranean area to be consistent
 1365 with the surface flux.

	MITgcm	ORCA	OM8
Surface flux	-2.7±4.8	0.0±3.3	-3.4±3.9
Gibraltar transport	4.2±0.2	4.5±0.8	4.4±0.4
Dardanelles transport	-	0.4±0.1	-
Heat loss due to mass loss (E-P-R)	-	-3.2±0.5	-
Total heat flux	1.5±4.8	1.7±3.4	1.0±3.9
ΔQ	1.4±0.1	1.5±0.1	0.9±0.1

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Figure 1. Detrended annual time series of temperature and salinity anomalies over the period 1961-2000 averaged over the Eastern Mediterranean (a,c) and the Western Mediterranean (b,d) for four different layers: 0-100 m, 100-500 m, 500-1000 m and 1000-2000 m. They have been estimated from the MEDISH database (green line) and from the three models: MITgcm (blue line), and OM8 (black line) and ORCA (dashed-dotted line).

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Figure 1. (Continued).

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Figure 2. Annual Time series of dense water formation rates (Sv) in the Gulf of Lions as obtained from the MITgcm (blue line), ORCA (dashed-dotted line) and OM8 (black line) models. The formation rates have been estimated for deep (>2000 m) water (top) and intermediate (200-500 m) water (bottom).

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Figure 3. Same as Figure 2 but for the Aegean Sea.

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1397 **Figure 4.** Same as Figure 2 but for the Adriatic Sea.

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1403 **Figure 5.** Distribution of total sea level trends for the period 1993-2000 as obtained
1404 from: a) altimetric SLA; b) the MITgcm model; c) the OM8 model; and d) the ORCA
1405 model. The black contour level indicates the 0 value. Units are mm/yr.

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1407 **Figure 6.** Monthly time series of Mediterranean mean sea level for the period 1993-
 1408 2000 estimated from altimetry data and the MITgcm, ORCA and OM8 models. A
 1409 centered 12-months moving average has been applied to all time series.

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1412 **Figure 7.** Distribution of total sea level trends for the period 1961-2000 as obtained
 1413 from: a) the sea level reconstruction by *Calafat and Gomis* [2009]; b) the MITgcm
 1414 model; c) the OM8 model; and d) the ORCA model. The black contour level indicates
 1415 the 0 value. Units are mm/yr.

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1417 **Figure 8.** Distribution of steric sea level (integrated from top to 700 m) trends for the
 1418 period 1961-2000 as obtained from: a) the MITgcm model; b) the OM8 model and c)
 1419 the ORCA model. Units are mm/yr in all cases.

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1427 **Figure 9.** Monthly time series for the period 1961-2000 of: a) Mediterranean mean sea
 1428 level estimated from the reconstruction, and the MITgcm and OM8 models and b) steric
 1429 component of mean sea level for the top 700 m estimated from the MITgcm, ORCA and
 1430 OM8 models and the MEDISH database (with errors bars). A centered 12-months
 1431 moving average has been applied to all time series.

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1437 **Figure 10.** Annual time series of averaged temperature (a), salinity (b) and potential

1438 density (c) in the Aegean Sea over the period 1961-2000 for the layers 0-100 m, 100-

1439 500 m, 500-1000 m and 1000-2000 m as given by the MITgcm (blue line), ORCA

1440 (dashed-dotted line) and OM8 (black line). The EMT period has been highlighted in
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Figure 10. (continued)

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1470 **Figure 11.** Monthly the total sea level for the period 1961-2000 estimated from the
1471 reconstruction (thick black line) and the MITgcm (blue line) and OM8 (thin black line)
1472 models averaged over: (a) the Aegean Sea; (b) the Ionian Sea. A centered 12-months
1473 moving average has been applied to all time series. Both the EMT and post-EMT
1474 periods have been highlighted in gray.

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1481 **Figure 12.** Yearly averaged time series of the net surface heat flux (top), the net heat
 1482 transport at the Gibraltar Strait (middle) and the total heat flux (sum of the other two)
 1483 (bottom). Note that values are normalized by the surface of the Mediterranean area to be
 1484 consistent with the surface flux. A centered 6-years moving average has been applied to
 1485 all time series.

a)

Eastern Mediterranean

b) Western Mediterranean

c)

Eastern Mediterranean

d)

Western Mediterranean

Gulf of Lions (>2000 m)

Gulf of Lions (200–500 m)

Aegean (>2000 m)

Aegean (200–500 m)

Adriatic (>2000 m)

Adriatic (200–500 m)

a)

b)

b)

c)

a)

b)

Net surface heat flux

Net Gibraltar heat transport

Total heat flux

